

Formation of Heterocyclic Compounds. Part III. Interaction of *cyclo*Hexanone-2-carboxylates with Phenols.

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The condensation between β -ketonic esters and phenols formed the subject of extensive investigation for the syntheses of benzo-pyrone derivatives by numerous workers (Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1844, **17**, 929, 1646, 2187 ; 1899, **32**, 3681 ; 1901, **34**, 423 ; Biginelli, *Gazzetta*, 1895, **24**, ii, 492 ; Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 38 ; Simonis and Petschek, *Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 2014 ; Simonis and Lechmann, *Ber.*, 1914, **47**, 697 ; Simonis and Remmert, *ibid.*, p. 2229 ; see also Heilborn, Barnes and Morton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 2569). Substituted acetoacetic esters like $\text{CH}_3\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}(\text{R})\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ ($\text{R}=\text{benzyl, phenyl, benzoyl}$), ethyl α -benzoyl- β -phenyl propionate and ethyl α -phenyl formylacetate (Jacobson and Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 424, 959, 1051), ethyl β -keto- γ -phenyl butyrate (Baker and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **127**, 1984), acetone dicarboxylic acid (Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 1606) and similar other β -ketonic esters also condense readily with phenols in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid, hydrogen chloride, and zinc chloride to give rise to α -pyrone derivatives.

As is well-known there are two possibilities in the mechanism of the reaction between a β -ketonic ester and phenol, one giving rise to a benzo- α -pyrone derivative (coumarin) as in (I) and the other to a benzo- γ -pyrone derivative (chromone) as in (II) :

On consulting the literature on the subject it was found that the usual course of reaction is according to (I), *i.e.*, in ordinary instances using sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid, or zinc chloride, β -ketonic esters give rise to benzo- α -pyrone derivatives. But using a condensing agent like phosphorous pentoxide, Simonis and his collaborators, however, (*loc. cit.*) prepared benzo- γ -pyrone derivatives from methyl

and ethyl derivatives of acetoacetic ester and phenols. The issue, therefore, is whether these reactions depend to a large extent on the reactivity of the methylene hydrogen atoms in the β -ketonic ester or on the condensing agent used. It is now generally admitted (see Baker and Robinson, *loc. cit.*) that the usual course of reaction is according to (1) and the benzo- γ -pyrone derivatives result only when the condensing agent is very strong such as phosphorus pentoxide.

It appeared to be of importance to ascertain whether a cyclic β -ketonic ester such as ethyl *cyclohexanone* 2-carboxylate in which the reactive methine group is situated in the nucleus has any influence in changing the course of such reactions.

After the work was continued for some time, it was noted that Dieckmann (*Annalen*, 1901, 317, 27), while describing the condensation of ethyl *cyclohexanone*-carboxylate and ethyl *cyclopentanone*-carboxylate with resorcinol, assumed that in such condensation α -pyrone derivatives are produced. As the influence of the reduced benzene ring of hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* (Sen-Gupta, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1347) and *cyclohexanone*-carboxylate (Sen and Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 51) was being studied at this time, a repetition of Dieckmann's results was considered necessary, specially in view of certain interesting criticisms put forward by Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2349) in connection with the γ -pyrone constitution of compounds described by Jacobson and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*).

Ethyl *cyclohexanone*-2-carboxylate may be regarded as a substituted β -ketonic ester and as such, if the explanation of Jacobson and Ghosh, that with the heavier substitution of the methylene hydrogen the chance of γ -pyrone formation increases, be taken as correct, then the products described in this investigation should be in all probability γ -pyrone derivatives, although both α - and γ -pyrone structures are possible:—

It has been proved, however, that a ketonitrile of the type $-\text{CO}-\overset{\cdot}{\text{C}}-\text{CN}$ condensing with a phenol gives rise to imino

compounds which on subsequent hydrolysis yields α -pyrones (Sonn, *Ber.*, 1918, 51, 821, 1829; Bargellini and Forti-Forli, *Gazzetta*, 1911, 41, i, 747; Baker, *loc. cit.*). Accordingly 2-cyano-cyclohexanone was condensed with resorcinol; the product obtained on hydrolysis of the intermediate compound was found to be identical with that obtained from ethyl cyclohexanone carboxylate and resorcinol. The identity of the two products was further established by preparing acetyl derivatives and comparing their properties. This would indicate that the products described below are α -pyrone and not γ -pyrone derivatives. The influence of condensing reagents in changing the course of reaction (*loc. cit.*) was next studied.

Accordingly attempt was made to produce the corresponding γ -pyrone derivatives by the use of phosphorus pentoxide but no product could be isolated.

However likely the α -pyrone constitution might thus appear to be, the behaviour with alkali of the *m*-cresol and *a*-naphthol condensation products with the ethyl cyclohexanone carboxylate was somewhat peculiar. As α -pyrones, they were expected to dissolve in warm or boiling alkali, even though their ultimate decomposition may be difficult. The resorcinol derivative naturally dissolved readily in alkali by virtue of the one hydroxyl group present in it; but when this hydroxyl group is acetylated benzoylated or alkylated, the resulting product no longer dissolves in alkali. Moreover, the condensation product with resorcinol, even on prolonged boiling with concentrated alkali, does not undergo any fission and can be recovered unchanged on acidification. It would appear from the reasonings above that in all probability the condensed ring form of the products inhibits dissolution in alkali—a fact which should not be at the present stage regarded as indicative of a γ -pyrone structure. On fusion, however, of the resorcinol derivative with caustic potash at 190°-200° for a few minutes, two products were isolated, one melting at 230° (the parent substance had m.p. 202°) and the other at 120° which was identified as benzoic acid. The product melting at 230° has not been definitely identified yet, but it is in all probability a dehydrogenated coumarin derivative.

The attendant formation of benzoic acid may be regarded as a proof of the dehydrogenation of the cyclohexane ring, as it is hardly to be expected that the benzoic acid should be derived from the resorcinol part of the compound. The usual experience under

such circumstances is to meet with resorcylic acid or resorcinol. In the present case also some resorcinol would be expected, which, however, could not be isolated probably on account of its low yield. Further investigation is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1. *Condensation of Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate with Resorcinol: Formation of 3:4-Tetrahydrobenzo-7-hydroxy-coumarin (III).*

Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate was prepared according to Kötze's method (*Annalen*, 1925, **342**, 346) and obtained as a colourless liquid, b.p. 104-107°/10 mm. The yield was about 65 per cent. of the weight of cyclohexanone used.

To a well cooled intimate mixture of resorcinol (2.5 g.) and ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (4 g.), well cooled strong sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) was gradually added with vigorous shaking. Within an hour a clear deep red solution having a violet fluorescence was obtained. The flask, being corked, was left overnight in an ice-chamber. Next day, the solution was poured over powdered ice when a pasty substance separated. This was purified by dissolving in dilute caustic soda solution and precipitating with dilute sulphuric acid. It crystallises from dilute alcohol in fine needles, melting at 201-202°.

To obtain a purer product in good yield the ester (2 g.) was intimately mixed with resorcinol (1.2 g.) and the mixture was slowly treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (6 c.c.) allowing the temperature to rise. The flask was shaken after each addition. After two hours the deep red solution was poured over powdered ice when a pasty mass was obtained. On adding a few c.c. of rectified spirit and stirring the mass, a solid separated. This was filtered, washed and dried. Crystallising from rectified spirit with the addition of a few drops of water, it melts at 202°. The yield is almost theoretical. (Found: C, 72.16; H, 5.69. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 72.22; H, 5.55 per cent.).

This condensation product (which was described by Dieckmann as 1:2-cyclotetramethylene umbelliferone melting at 203-204°) readily dissolves in dilute alkali or alkali carbonate to a yellow solution from which it is reprecipitated unchanged by acid. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it with a violet fluorescence; from the acid solution the product can be recovered on dilution

with water. Ferric chloride imparts no coloration to its alcoholic solution.

Attempt to condense by Phosphorus Pentoxide.—Resorcinol (5 g.), cyclohexanone carboxylate (5 g.) and phosphorus pentoxide (8 g.) were heated on a water-bath for half an hour and then over a sand-bath for a few minutes. It was then treated with resorcinol (5 g.) and the oxide (7 g.) and again heated on a water-bath for about 3 hours. On adding water to the product and on subsequent usual treatment, no condensation product was obtained; only a tarry matter separated out.

Next a mixture of resorcinol (2.5 g.), the ester (4 g.) and the oxide (16 g.) was taken in xylene (about 60 c.c.) and heated under reflux on a sand-bath for 4 hours. In this case nothing but a resinous product separated out after subsequent treatment of the reacted mass.

Action of Alkali on 3:4-Tetrahydrobenzo-7-hydroxycoumarin.—The coumarin derivative (3 g.) was dissolved in potassium hydroxide (20 g. in 20 c.c. water) and heated under reflux on a sand-bath for about 5 hours. The solution was found to contain an oily liquid which was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was taken, ether evaporated off when a faint yellow coloured liquid (about 0.5 c.c.) having an odour like that of cyclohexanone was obtained. On treatment with sodium acetate and semicarbazide hydrochloride a solid product was obtained with much difficulty. On crystallisation from dilute rectified spirit it melted at 175-176° sintering at 160°. The mixed m.p. of this substance with the semicarbazone of cyclohexanone (m.p. 170°) was 142-143°.

The alkaline solution on acidification with dilute sulphuric acid gave a solid product which was dissolved in caustic soda solution and treated with carbon dioxide. The solid separated was found to be the original substance. The filtrate was again acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and shaken up with ether. The ethereal solution on evaporation gave a minute quantity of an oily product which on scratching turned into a pasty magma-like substance. Thus it was found that the major portion of the substance remained unchanged.

Next the coumarin derivative (3 g.) was fused with solid caustic potash (15 g.) at 190-200° for about ten minutes. The fused mass was dissolved in water and filtered. The dark coloured filtrate on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave a product (about 0.8 g.) which on crystallisation from dilute alcohol melts

at 230°. It is probably a dehydrogenated coumarin derivative. (Found: C, 73.23; H, 4.12. This corresponds to the empirical formula $C_{13}H_8O_3$, which requires C, 75.58; H, 3.77 per cent.)

The substance dissolves like the parent compound, in alkali and alkali carbonate with a yellow coloration. It gives a light green fluorescence with concentrated sulphuric acid. Ferric chloride solution gives no coloration. The *benzoyl* derivative prepared in pyridine solution melts at 195°. It is insoluble in alkali or alkaline carbonate, but concentrated sulphuric acid gives a grass-green fluorescence.

The filtrate, after acidification with hydrochloric acid and extraction with ether, gives a viscous mass from which benzoic acid can be isolated by extraction with petroleum ether.

Acetyl Derivative of the above Coumarin Derivative.—The substance (1.4 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (0.8 g.) and fused sodium acetate (1 g.) under reflux on a sand-bath for one hour. The solution was then poured over water when a solid separated (yield, 90 per cent.). On crystallising from alcohol it melted at 186–187°. (Found: C, 70.23; H, 5.58. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 69.77; H, 5.43 per cent.)

Methyl Ether.—This was prepared by treating the alkaline solution of the substance with excess of dimethyl sulphate. It crystallises from dilute alcohol in fine needle-like crystals melting at 121–122°. (Found: C, 72.83; H, 6.1. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 73.04; H, 6.09 per cent.)

Benzoyl Derivative.—The substance (0.5 g.) was dissolved in pyridine and treated with a few drops of benzoyl chloride; a solid separated. The tube was warmed and water was added, when an oil was obtained. On allowing the oil to cool and scratching with a rod, a solid separated out which on crystallisation from rectified spirit melted at 157° sintering a few degrees earlier. (Found: C, 74.84; H, 5.19. $C_{20}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.0 per cent.). All these derivatives are insoluble in alkali or alkaline carbonate.

Condensation of 2-Cyanocyclohexanone with Resorcinol.—2-Cyano-cyclohexanone was prepared from 2-hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone and hydroxylamine hydrochloride according to the method of Auwers, Bahr and Frese (*Annalen*, 1925, **441**, 43, 68) and obtained as a colorless liquid, b. p. 149–150°/25 mm. (yield, 29 per cent.).

Concentrated sulphuric acid (30 c.c.) was slowly added to a mixture of cyano-cyclohexanone and resorcinol without allowing the

temperature to rise. After 36 hours the reaction product was poured over powdered ice, when a yellow solid (3 g.) was obtained after a few hours. This nitrogen containing compound was insoluble in alcohol, acetic acid water, and in most ordinary organic solvents, but was soluble in conc. sulphuric acid and alkali. It melted at 290°. The substance (2 g.) was heated with a 15 per cent. solution of caustic potash (25 c.c.) under reflux for 3½ hours when a strong smell of ammonia was perceived. The dark liquid formed, on dilution with water and on acidification with hydrochloric acid, yielded a solid product which on crystallising from dilute alcohol melted at 198°. The mixed melting point of this compound with that obtained from ethyl *cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate* and resorcinol (m.p. 202°) was 201°.

The above compound was acetylated by heating under reflux for an hour with acetic anhydride and fused potassium acetate. The product obtained on crystallisation from alcohol, separated in needles, m. p. 184-185°. The mixed melting point of this derivative with the acetyl derivative described above (*loc. cit.*) is 186-187°. Thus the two products, one obtained from ethyl *cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate* and resorcinol, and the other from 2-cyano-*cyclohexanone* and resorcinol, are identical.

Condensation of Ethyl cycloHexanone-2-carboxylate and m-Cresol: Formation of 3:4-Tetrahydrobenzo-7-methylcoumarin.

Concentrated sulphuric acid (25 c.c) was gradually added to an intimate mixture of *m*-cresol (4 g.) and the ester (6.5 g.) with shaking and without allowing the temperature to rise. A dark red solution was soon obtained. Next morning the solution was poured over ice water when an oil separated, which on treatment with alcohol turned into a solid mass (about 4 g.; yield, 50 per cent.). It crystallised from diluted rectified spirit in long needles melting at 119°. (Found: C, 78.57; H, 6.49. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 78.50; H, 5.54 per cent.).

This coumarin derivative is insoluble even in a strong caustic soda solution. On boiling the solution the substance melts, and forms an oil which again solidifies on cooling. It is soluble in strong sulphuric acid without any coloration or fluorescence; from this acid solution it can be recovered unchanged on dilution with water.

*Condensation of α -Naphthol with cycloHexanone-2-carboxylate :
Formation of 3:4-Tetrahydrobenzonaphthacoumarin :*

α -Naphthol (3.2 g.) was dissolved in the ester (4.2 g.) and the solution was slowly treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (6 c.c.). The mixture became warm and a deep red solution was obtained. Next morning it was found that a certain amount of solid had separated out. The contents of the flask were poured over powdered ice and the solid formed collected (6 g., yield, theoretical). In another preparation it was found that it is unnecessary to keep the reaction mixture over-night. The reaction product was found to be usual after pouring the liquid over powdered ice even after 2 hours. Crystallising from alcohol it melted at 190°. (Found: C, 82.52; H, 5.86. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 81.6; H, 5.6 per cent.).

This coumarin derivative gives no coloration with ferric chloride, is insoluble in alkali but soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid with yellow coloration and a sea-green fluorescence.

Nitro Derivative.—To concentrated sulphuric acid (1 c.c.), strong nitric acid (1 c.c.) was carefully added, and to the mixture a solution of the above compound (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid was added. After the reaction had subsided, the flask was cooled and the contents poured over powdered ice when a yellow substance separated. Crystallising from glacial acetic acid thrice, it melted at 244°, sintering a few degrees earlier. (Found: N, 5.01. $C_{17}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 4.75 per cent.).

Condensation of Phloroglucinol and Ethyl 5-Methyl-cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate: Formation of 3:4-Tetrahydro-4'-methyl-benzo-5:7-dihydroxycoumarin.

The ester was prepared in the usual way from *m*-methyl-cyclohexanone which yields about 61 per cent. of its weight of 5-methyl-cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate as a colorless liquid, b.p. 136-140°/25 mm.

The ester (6 g.) and phloroglucinol (4 g.) were mixed with glacial acetic acid (4 c.c.) and finely powdered fused zinc chloride (27 g.) was added. The mixture was heated at about 115° for 5 hours with continuous stirring when it turned into a viscous mass. Next morning it was boiled with water when a yellow granular substance (about 6 g.) was obtained (yield, 75 to 80 per cent.). It was difficult to crystallise it. The substance was dissolved in ether and petroleum-ether was then added when a product was obtained. This was again dissolved in ether and treated with animal charcoal. From the filtrate on spontaneous evaporation, a white solid was obtained, melting at 264-66°, sintering a few degrees earlier. (Found: C, 68.0; H, 5.49. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.29; H, 5.69 per cent.).

It is easily soluble in warm alkali, and in concentrated sulphuric acid with yellow coloration but with no fluorescence. Ferric chloride imparts no coloration to its alcoholic solution.

Condensation of Orcinol and 5-Methyl-cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate: Formation of 3:4-Tetrahydro-4'-methylbenzo-5-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin.

To an intimate mixture of the ester (3 g.), and orcinol (2 g.), concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) was gradually added with shaking and without allowing the temperature to rise. Soon a clear red solution was obtained. It was left overnight. Next day the red solution was poured over ice when a pasty mass separated. On adding rectified spirit a substance (3 g.) was obtained in granular form (yield, 75 per cent.). Crystallising from rectified spirit diluted with a few drops of water it was obtained in fine needles, m.p. 249°. (Found: C, 73.53; H, 6.81. $C_{14}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 73.77; H, 6.56 per cent.).

It is soluble in caustic soda solution with yellow coloration but imparts no coloration to alcoholic ferric chloride. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it with a yellow coloration.

Condensation of Pyrogallol with 5-Methyl-cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate: Formation of 3:4-Tetrahydro-4'-methylbenzo-7:8-dihydroxy-coumarin.

A mixture of pyrogallol (2.5 g.) and the ester (3.7 g.) was treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) in the usual way. Next morning the deep red solution obtained, was poured over powdered ice when a grey coloured substance (4.8 g.) was obtained. It crystallises from methyl alcohol in needles, m.p. 231°. (Found: C, 68.1; H, 5.89. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.29; H, 5.69 per cent.).

The condensation product readily dissolves in alkali from which it may be reprecipitated unchanged by the addition of acid. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it with yellow coloration and emerald green fluorescence; from the acid solution it may be recovered on dilution with water. Ferric chloride imparts no coloration to its alcoholic solution.